

Clinical and Microbiological Profile of Ventilator-Associated Pneumonia in Intensive Care Unit of Tertiary Care Hospital

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Abstract

Introduction: Ventilator-associated pneumonia (VAP) is a common hospital-acquired infection in mechanically ventilated patients, leading to increased mortality, ICU stays, and healthcare costs. VAP is primarily caused by the aspiration of oropharyngeal organisms into the distal bronchi, either directly or via reflux from the stomach. Less common routes include hematogenous spread from remote infections or contamination from medical equipment. The incidence of VAP ranges from 6.8% to 44%, significantly impacting hospital stay length, mortality rates, and financial burden. Effective preventive strategies are crucial in managing this condition.

Methods: This study was conducted in SGRDIMS, Vallah, Amritsar. Patients were selected from ICUs based on inclusion and exclusion criteria. Clinically suspected patients, according to CDC criteria, were scored using the Chronic Pulmonary Infection Score (CPIS), considering clinical, microbiological, and radiological signs. Variables noted for each patient included age, gender, CPIS, diagnosis at ICU admission, duration of ventilation, antibiotics received, samples submitted for confirmation of etiological agents, endotracheal aspirate, suction tip culture, type of organism recovered, susceptibility profile, and clinical outcome.

Results: Out of 362 patients, 231 (63.8%) were males and 131 (36.2%) were females, with a male-to-female ratio of 1.76:1. The most common comorbidities observed were hypertension (53.9%), type 2 diabetes mellitus (52.8%), coronary artery disease (19.06%), obstructive sleep apnea (14.08%), cerebrovascular accident (6.4%), chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (4.14%), and bronchial asthma (3.59%). Supine position was a risk factor in 99.7% of patients, with nasogastric tube use at 99.44%, and sedation at 98.1%. While 39.2% of patients had a CPIS score greater than 6, the majority (60.8%) had a CPIS score less than 6. Among the patients, 39.23% developed VAP after being intubated and mechanically ventilated for 48 hours or more. The majority of isolates obtained were gram-negative bacteria (98.44%), with only 1.56% being gram-positive. Among the 128 organisms isolated, the most common was *Klebsiella Pneumoniae* (41.40%), followed by *Acinetobacter Baumannii* (21.09%). Among the 142 patients who developed VAP, 42.25% had successful outcomes, while 57.74% did not survive. The most common clinical features of VAP included fever, crepitation, and tachypnea. The mean duration of mechanical ventilation for patients who developed VAP was 9.09 ± 2.747 days, compared to those who did not develop VAP. Patients with VAP had notably longer ICU and hospital stays compared to those without VAP.

Conclusion: This study provides a comprehensive analysis of ventilator-associated pneumonia (VAP), including its epidemiology, microbial etiology, antibiotic resistance, and patient outcomes. Key prognostic indicators such as body temperature, total leukocyte count (TLC), inotropic support, tracheal secretion characteristics, and the presence of VAP are identified. The findings underscore the importance of tailored prevention and management strategies to improve patient outcomes and advocate for ongoing surveillance and evidence-based approaches to address this challenging infection.

Keywords: Chronic Pulmonary Infection Score, CDC, MDR, VAP.

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Introduction

Ventilator-associated pneumonia (VAP) is a critical ICU condition occurring more than 48 hours after intubation and mechanical ventilation, identified by

new or worsening chest X-ray shadows, fever, abnormal white blood cell counts, changes in sputum, and the presence of a causative

pathogen.[1] It affects 9% to 27% of ventilated ICU patients and significantly increases morbidity and mortality rates.[2] In India, the crude mortality rate for ICU patients with pneumonia is 67.4%, with 40% of these deaths due to infections like VAP.[3]

VAP has two onset patterns:

Early-onset VAP (within 96 hours of MV) responds better to antibiotics.

Late-onset VAP (after 96 hours of MV) involves multidrug-resistant bacteria like *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Acinetobacter Baumannii*, leading to higher mortality and morbidity.[4]

The highest incidence of VAP occurs within the first five days of ICU admission, with a daily risk of 3%, which decreases to 2% per day for days 5-10 and 1% thereafter.[2] Early diagnosis and prompt antibiotic therapy are crucial, as delays increase mortality.[2,4]

Diagnosis involves clinical, radiological, and microbiological assessments, using samples from bronchoscopic (e.g., BAL) or non-bronchoscopic techniques (e.g., endotracheal aspirates).[5] However, endotracheal aspirates might have lower sensitivity compared to bronchoscopic methods.[6]

Common pathogens include *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Acinetobacter* species, *Klebsiella Pneumoniae*, *Enterobacter* species, and MRSA, many of which are multidrug-resistant due to beta-lactamase production.

VAP significantly impacts clinical outcomes and healthcare costs, emphasizing the need for effective diagnosis and treatment strategies.

Aim and Objectives

Aim of the Study

To determine the incidence, clinical and microbiological profile of Ventilator Associated Pneumonia in ICUs of tertiary care hospital.

Objectives of the Study

To assess the incidence of VAP in patients on mechanical ventilation admitted in ICUs.

To assess the clinical profile and risk factors for development of VAP in ICUs.

To determine the microbiological profile and prevalence of MDR in patients with VAP.

Material and methods

Study design: Observational Cross sectional study.

Study period: The study period was from 01st January 2023 to 31st March 2024.

Study setting: The study was conducted at Sri Guru Ram Das Institute of Medical Sciences and Research Vallah, Amritsar

Sample size: 362 patients

Study Population:

The research encompassed patients requiring ventilatory support for over 48 hours in various specialized intensive care units, such as the Medical Intensive Care Unit (MICU), Surgical Intensive Care Unit (SICU), Main ICU, Cardiac Care Unit (CCU), Emergency Intensive Care Unit (E-ICU), Pediatric Intensive Care Unit (P-ICU), and Cardiothoracic and Vascular Surgery (CTVS) unit, all of whom satisfied the specified criteria.

Inclusion Criteria: -

1. Patients older than 12 years.
2. Patients undergoing mechanical ventilation for more than 48 hours with the radiological and clinical parameters indicative of Ventilator Associated pneumonia. The parameters are presence of a new or progressive radiographic infiltrate plus at least two of the following features which include fever greater than 38°C, leucocytosis or leukopenia and purulent lower respiratory secretions.

Exclusion Criteria: -

1. Patients with pneumonia prior to mechanical ventilation
2. Patients developing pneumonia within 48 hours of mechanical ventilation.
3. Patients who are severely immunocompromised such as Acquired immune deficiency syndrome (AIDS), organ transplant patients, terminal stages of malignancy are excluded.

Methods

Patient data comprises demographic information such as age, gender, address, and date of admission, as well as clinical details including level of consciousness, risk factors (e.g., nasogastric tube, enteral nutrition, antacid or histamine type 2 blocker therapy), underlying diseases, date of intubation/tracheostomy, duration of mechanical ventilation, and prior antibiotic use.

Additionally, therapy and other relevant activities were diligently documented.

Under aseptic precautions endotracheal aspirates were obtained using a 22-inch, No.12 F suction catheter and collected in a mucus collector. The catheter was gently introduced through the endotracheal tube for at least 25-26 cm length. Gentle aspiration was then performed without instilling saline and the catheter was withdrawn from the ET tube, 2mL of normal saline was injected with a sterile syringe to flush the exudate into a sterile container for collection.[7]

Under aseptic and antiseptic precautions, samples were collected from the patients and transported immediately to bacteriology section of microbiology department of Sri Guru Ram Das Institute of

Medical Sciences and Research for culture and sensitivity testing.

Data was recorded in a Microsoft excel spread sheet and analysed using Statistical Package for the IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows, Version 23.0. Armonk, NY: IBM Corp., Chicago

Continuous data was presented as mean with standard deviation. Categorical data was expressed as percentages. Numerical variables were normally distributed and analysed using independent t- test. Categorical variables were analysed using chi square test. P- value less than 0.05 was taken as statistically significant.

The results were analysed and compared to previous studies to draw relevant conclusions.

AST (Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing) was done using WHO approved Kirby Bauer's Disc Diffusion method using designated antibiotic discs (6 mm size) impregnated with fixed amount of drug on a lawn culture of test organism on Mueller Hinton Agar (MHA) that is incubated for 24 hours at 37°C. Results obtained (Sensitive / Intermediate / Resistant) were measured by clearing of growth around each disc and interpreted as per CLSI guidelines.[8,9] Samples were run in Automated Vitek-2 (bioMerieux) in parallel for identification and AST.

Results and Discussion

Table 1: Distribution of patients according to gender

Gender	Number (n)	Percentage (%)
Male	231	63.8
Female	131	36.2
Total	362	100

Figure 1: Distribution of patients according to gender.

Table 2: Distribution of patients according to age group.

Age group(years)	Number (N)	Percentage (%)
<40	90	24.93
41-60	141	38.78
61-80	123	34.07
>80	8	2.22
Total	362	100

Figure 2: Distribution of patients according to age group.

Table 3: Incidence of VAP.

Incidence of VAP	Number(N)	Percentage (%)
Yes	142	39.23
No	220	60.77
Total	362	100

Figure 3: Incidence of vap.

Table 4: Distribution of study participants according to vap types.

VAP Types	Number (N)	Percentage (%)
Early onset VAP (within 96 hours of MV)	113	79.57
Late onset VAP (after 96 hours of MV)	29	20.42
Total	142	100

Figure 4: Distribution of study participants according to vap types.

Table 5: Distribution according to type of organism isolated.

Type of organism isolated	Number (N)	Percentage (%)
Klebsiella Pneumonia	53	41.40
Acinetobacter Baumannii	27	21.09
Enterobacter cloacae complex	21	16.40
Pseudomonas aeruginosa	15	11.71
Proteus Mirabilis	2	1.56
Pseudomonas + Klebsiella	2	1.56
Klebsiella + Acinetobacter	2	1.56
Staph aureus	2	1.56
Sphingomonas Paucimobilis	1	0.78
Enterobacter Aerogenes	1	0.78
Serratia Marcences	1	0.78
Klebsiella + Proteus mirabilis	1	0.78
Total	128	100

Figure 5: Distribution according to type of organism isolated.

Table 6: Clinical features in early and late onset vap

Clinical Features	VAP early onset		VAP late onset	
	N	%	N	%
Fever	104	92.03	23	79.3
Tachypnoea	104	92.03	18	62.06
Fall in SpO2	80	70.79	21	72.41
Crepitations	88	77.87	21	72.41
Leucocytosis	80	70.79	18	62.06
Chest X ray				
Local infiltrate	15	13.27	10	34.48
Diffuse infiltrate	98	86.72	19	65.51
Total	113	100	29	100

Figure 6: Clinical features in early and late onset vap

Table 7: Distribution of organisms in early and late onset vap.

Type of organism	Early onset VAP	Late onset VAP
Klebsiella Pneumonia	36	17
Enterobacter cloacae complex	18	3
Acinetobacter Baumannii	18	9
Pseudomonas aeruginosa	11	4

Staph aureus	2	0
Proteus mirabilis	2	0
Enterobacter Aerogenes	1	0
Sphingomonas Paucimobilis	1	0
Serratia Marcescens	1	0

Figure 7: Distribution of organisms in early and late onset vap.

Table 8: Antibiotic sensitivity pattern of isolated organism.

Organism	E. Coli (n=21)		Pseudomonas aeruginosa (n=15)		Klebsiella pneumoniae (n=55)		Acinetobacter baumannii (n=28)		Enterobacter aerogenes (n=1)		Staphylococcus aureus (n=2)	
	Sensitive	Resistant	Sensitive	Resistant	Sensitive	Resistant	Sensitive	Resistant	Sensitive	Resistant	Sensitive	Resistant
Piperacillin/Tazobactam	6 (28.6)	15 (71.4)	4 (26.7)	11 (73.3)	13 (23.6)	42 (76.4)	3 (10.7)	25 (89.3)	0(0)	1 (100)	1(50)	1 (50)
Cefoperazone/sulbactam	9 (42.9)	12 (57.1)	3 (20)	12 (80)	15 (27.3)	40 (72.2)	5 (17.9)	23 (82.1)	0(0)	1 (100)	1(50)	1 (50)
Ertapenem	9 (42.9)	12 (57.1)	8 (53.3)	7 (46.7)	16 (29.1)	39 (70.9)	3 (10.7)	25 (89.3)	0(0)	1 (100)	1(50)	1 (50)
Imipenem	12 (57.1)	9 (42.9)	10 (66.7)	5 (33.3)	16 (29.1)	39 (70.9)	3 (10.7)	25 (89.3)	0(0)	1 (100)	1(50)	1 (50)
Meropenem	13 (61.9)	8 (38.1)	11 (73.3)	4 (26.7)	17 (30.9)	38 (69.1)	4 (14.3)	24 (85.7)	0(0)	1 (100)	1(50)	1 (50)
Amikacin	15 (71.4)	6 (28.6)	11 (73.3)	4 (26.7)	18 (32.7)	37 (67.3)	4 (14.3)	24 (85.7)	0(0)	1 (100)	1(50)	1 (50)
Gentamicin	9 (42.9)	12 (57.1)	5 (33.3)	10 (66.7)	18 (32.7)	37 (67.3)	3 (10.7)	25 (89.3)	0(0)	1 (100)	0(0)	2 (100)
Tigecycline	14 (66.7)	7 (33.3)	1 (6.7)	14 (93.3)	21 (38.2)	34 (61.8)	4 (14.3)	24 (85.7)	0(0)	1 (100)	1(50)	1 (50)
Cefepime	7 (33.3)	14 (66.7)	3 (20)	12 (80)	11 (20)	44 (80)	2 (7.1)	26 (92.9)	0(0)	1 (100)	0(0)	2 (100)
Ciprofloxacin	0 (0)	21 (100)	1 (6.7)	14 (93.3)	2 (3.6)	53 (96.4)	0 (0)	28 (100)	0(0)	1 (100)	0(0)	2 (100)
Levofloxacin	0 (0)	21 (100)	1 (6.7)	14 (93.3)	2 (3.6)	53 (96.4)	0 (0)	28 (100)	0(0)	1 (100)	0(0)	2 (100)
Doripenem	0 (0)	21 (100)	0 (0)	15 (100)	2 (3.6)	53 (96.4)	0 (0)	28 (100)	0(0)	1 (100)	0(0)	2 (100)

Ceftriaxone+Sulbactam+Disodium EDTA	4 (19)	17 (81)	0 (0)	15 (100)	26 (47.3)	29 (52.7)	15(53.6)	13 (46.4)	1(100)	0 (0)	0(0)	2 (100)
Polymyxin -B	0 (0)	21 (100)	0 (0)	15 (100)	3 (5.5)	52 (94.5)	4 (14.3)	24 (85.7)	1(100)	0 (0)	0(0)	2 (100)
Minocycline	0 (0)	21 (100)	0 (0)	15 (100)	0 (0)	55 (100)	4 (14.3)	24 (85.7)	0(0)	1 (100)	0(0)	2 (100)
Ceftriaxone	1 (4.8)	20 (95.2)	0 (0)	15 (100)	1 (1.8)	54 (98.2)	1 (3.6)	27 (96.4)	0(0)	1 (100)	0(0)	2 (100)

Table 9: Survival outcomes based on vap status.

	Survived	Not Survived	P- value
VAP present	60	82	<0.001
VAP absent	150	70	

Figure 8: Survival outcomes based on vap status.

Discussion

In our study on 362 patients, 231/362 (63.8%) were male and 131/362 (36.2%) female, consistent with other studies done by Chastre and Fagon.[10] Bouadma et al.[11] and Kollef et al.[12] suggested higher male preponderance to VAP due to factors like smoking, chronic lung diseases, hormonal differences, and immune response variations. While many studies suggest a higher prevalence of ventilator-associated pneumonia (VAP) in males, there are also studies indicating a higher or comparable incidence in females. For instance, a systematic review by Kharel et al.[13] covering VAP incidence in the WHO Southeast Asian region found varied results across different studies, with some reporting a higher prevalence in female patients. This review highlights that the incidence of VAP and its associated factors can differ significantly based on regional healthcare practices and patient demographics.

Age distribution showed 141/362 (38.78%) of patients were 41-60 years old, 123/362 (34.07%) were 61-80 years, 90/362 (24.93%) were under 40 years, and 8/362 (2.22%) were over 80 years. This aligns with studies done by Koenig and Truwit.[14] and Vincent et al.[15] indicating higher VAP incidence in middle-aged and older adults who

are more likely to be in critical care and have reduced immune function and increased comorbidities. However, a study done by Kharel et al.[13] shown a higher incidence of VAP among younger adults. This research conducted in Southeast Asia found a significant number of VAP cases in patients under 40 years old, challenging the notion that middle-aged and older adults are the most affected.

These findings suggest that while middle-aged and older adults are commonly reported as having higher VAP rates, there are notable exceptions where younger populations also exhibit significant VAP incidence.

Hypertension (53.9%) and Type II diabetes mellitus (52.8%) were the most prevalent comorbidities, in concordance with findings by Vincent et al.[15] and Girou et al.[16] Other significant comorbidities included CAD (19.1%) and OSA (14.08%), which align with studies by Restrepo et al.[17] However, less common conditions like hypothyroidism, CLD, CKD, and seizure disorders may also impact patient outcomes. In contrast to our findings, research conducted by Kharel et al.[13] in the WHO Southeast Asian region highlighted varying comorbidity patterns, with a higher prevalence of

COPD and fewer instances of hypertension and diabetes compared to Western populations.

The most prevalent VAP risk factors included supine positioning (99.7%), nasogastric tube use (99.44%), sedation (98.1%), and antacid use (97.5%). These factors are well-documented in the literature. Similar to observations of Herzig et al.[18] who linked antacid use to increased gastric pH and bacterial overgrowth, promoting aspiration.

Clinical Pulmonary Infection Score (CPIS) was studied in the context of VAP. Among the 362 patients who we analyzed, 39.2% had a CPIS score greater than 6, indicating a high likelihood of VAP diagnosis while the majority, comprising 60.8% of patients, had a CPIS score below 6.

The CPIS serves as a reliable tool for diagnosing VAP, with a threshold score of 6 or higher indicating a heightened probability of the condition. Research by Fartoukh et al.[19] demonstrated a sensitivity of 72% and a specificity of 85% for VAP diagnosis using this threshold. Similarly, Zilberberg and Shorr[20] reported a positive predictive value of 92% for VAP diagnosis with a CPIS score of 6 or higher. However a review by Póvoa et al.[21] emphasized the substantial inter-observer variability and the moderate diagnostic performance of the CPIS, arguing that it should not be solely relied upon without additional clinical and bacteriological data. They pointed out that the CPIS often fails to correlate well with more definitive diagnostic methods such as lung histopathology or quantitative cultures from bronchoalveolar lavage (BAL)

Of the 362 patients included in our study, 142/362 (39.23%) developed VAP after being intubated and mechanically ventilated for more than 48 hours. This incidence rate aligns with previous studies reporting rates ranging from 8.0% to 28.8% of the population at risk, with event rates ranging from 1.4 to 16.5 per 1000 ventilation days. As study done by Papazian et al.[22] reported the incidence of VAP ranges from 5% to 40 % among mechanically ventilated patients, with the highest risk being early in course of hospitalization. In contrast Kollef et al.[23] reported a lower incidence of VAP, with rates around 10% in certain ICU settings. This variation can be attributed to differences in patient populations, ICU protocols, and definitions used for diagnosing VAP.

Among the 142 patients diagnosed with VAP, 113/142 (79.57%) had early-onset VAP, occurring within 96 hours of mechanical ventilation, while 29/142 (20.42%) had late-onset VAP, developing after 96 hours of ventilation. This distribution is consistent with prior research indicating a higher incidence of early-onset VAP compared to late-onset VAP. A study by Kollef et al.[23] found that 73% of VAP cases were early-onset, while 27% were late-onset. Similarly, a study by Chastre and

Fagon[10] reported that 50-60% of VAP cases were early-onset, and 40-50% were late-onset. In contrast to our study, study by Reechaipichitkul W. et al.[24] found that out of 190 VAP patients, 148 (77.9%) had late-onset VAP, while only 42 (22.1%) had early-onset VAP.

The distribution of organisms isolated from patients with VAP reveals that 53/128 (41.40%) of isolates were *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, 27/128 (21.09%) were *Acinetobacter baumannii*, 21/128 (16.40%) were *Enterobacter cloacae* complex, 15/128 (11.71%) were *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and 2/128 (1.56%) were *Proteus mirabilis*. Other isolates included *Sphingomonas paucimobilis*, *Enterobacter aerogenes*, *Serratiamarcescens*, and *Staphylococcus aureus*. Additionally, 1.56% of isolates were polymicrobial, including combinations such as *Pseudomonas* + *Klebsiella*, *Klebsiella* + *Acinetobacter*, *Klebsiella* + *Proteus mirabilis*. A study conducted Reechaipichitkul W. et al.[24] at Srinagarind Hospital in Thailand found that the causative pathogens of VAP were predominantly Gram-negative bacteria (97.4%), with the most common pathogens being *Acinetobacter baumannii* (52.1%), *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (15.3%), and *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia* (13.2%).

The clinical outcomes for our VAP patients show that 42.25% survived, while 57.74% did not survive. This high mortality rate is consistent with previous findings by Torres et al.[25] who found a mortality rate of 44.4%. A study done by Le Pape M. et al.[26] reported a mortality rate of 50% for patients with VAP. They concluded that VAP is a substantial contributor to poor outcomes in mechanically ventilated patients, consistent with our findings. However in contrast a study done by Nseir S et al.[27] observed a much lower mortality rate in VAP patients, with only about 30% of patients not surviving. The authors suggest that the differences in outcomes could be due to variations in patient demographics, underlying health conditions, and differences in ICU practices and VAP management.

Gender-wise, 64.78% of our VAP cases were observed in males, and 35.21% in females, reflecting similar trends in studies by Rello et al.[28] who noted a male-to-female ratio of 1.4:1, and by Torres et al.[25] who found 68.3% of VAP cases in males.

In our study we observed that 73.23% of VAP patients had type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) with HbA1c > 6.5%, 61.26% had hypertension (HTN), 16.19% had coronary artery disease (CAD), 14.08% had obstructive sleep apnea (OSA), 8.4% had chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), 7.04% had bronchial asthma, 6.33% had a history of cerebrovascular accident (CVA), and 2.81% had chronic liver disease (CLD). These findings align with Rello et al.[28] and Nseir et al.[27] who identified COPD and diabetes as VAP risk factors.

Our study reveals that 64.78% of VAP patients were alcoholics, and 3.5% were smokers. This aligns with Rello et al.[28] and Nseir et al.[27] who identified alcohol abuse as a VAP risk factor.

Clinical feature wise in early and late onset VAP we observed that, in early-onset VAP (113 cases), fever and tachypnea were observed in 92.03% of patients each, crepitations in 77.87%, fall in SpO₂ and leukocytosis in 70.79% each. Chest X-rays showed localized infiltrates in 13.27% and diffuse infiltrates in 86.72% of patients. In late-onset VAP (29 cases), fever was seen in 79.3%, fall in SpO₂ and crepitations in 72.41% each, and tachypnea and leukocytosis in 62.06% each. Chest X-rays showed localized infiltrates in 34.48% and diffuse infiltrates in 65.51% of patients. These findings align with Rello et al.[28] and Torres et al.[25] who reported similar clinical features and highlighted more acute symptoms in early-onset VAP due to less virulent pathogens.

In our study of the distribution of organisms responsible for early and late-onset VAP, we found significant differences in microbial prevalence between the two categories. *Klebsiella pneumoniae* was the predominant pathogen in early-onset VAP, followed by *Enterobacter cloacae* complex, *Acinetobacter Baumannii*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. In contrast, late-onset VAP was most frequently associated with *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, followed by *Acinetobacter Baumannii*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Enterobacter cloacae* complex. These findings align with studies by Kollef et al.[23] and Chastre and Fagon[10] highlighting the consistent prominence of these pathogens in VAP cases and the importance of targeted antimicrobial strategies for effective management and prevention.

Our analysis of antibiotic susceptibility testing on *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*) isolates revealed a mixed pattern of sensitivity and resistance among various antibiotics. Carbapenems and aminoglycosides showed moderate to high levels of sensitivity (42.9% to 71.4%), while fluoroquinolones, cephalosporins, and other antibiotics exhibited alarmingly high resistance rates (almost 100%). These findings are consistent with studies by Livermore et al.[29] highlighting the evolving nature of antibiotic resistance among *E. coli* isolates and the need for ongoing surveillance and tailored antimicrobial strategies.

Similarly, our assessment of antibiotic susceptibility testing on *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* isolates revealed varied levels of effectiveness among antibiotics. Certain antibiotics, including carbapenems and aminoglycosides, exhibited moderate efficacy (53.3% to 73.3%), while others showed lower effectiveness or complete resistance (100%). These findings are consistent with studies

by Livermore et al.[29] emphasizing the challenges posed by multidrug-resistant *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* infections and the need for novel therapeutic strategies.

In our study, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* isolates demonstrated a broad spectrum of susceptibility to various antibiotics, indicating significant challenges in managing infections caused by this pathogen. Ceftriaxone + Sulbactam + Disodium EDTA exhibited the highest sensitivity (47.3%), followed by Tigecycline (38.2%), while antibiotics like Ciprofloxacin, Levofloxacin, and Doripenem had very low efficacy (3.6%). These findings align with studies by Lautenbach et al.[30] and the Sentry Antimicrobial Surveillance Program, highlighting high resistance rates to fluoroquinolones and cephalosporins among *Klebsiella pneumoniae* isolates. Additionally, increasing resistance to carbapenems, such as Imipenem and Meropenem, underscores the need for new therapeutic options and effective antimicrobial stewardship.

Similarly, our analysis of antibiotic susceptibility in *Acinetobacter Baumannii* isolates revealed a range of resistance patterns, with Ceftriaxone + Sulbactam + Disodium EDTA demonstrating the highest sensitivity (53.6%). Ciprofloxacin, Levofloxacin, and Doripenem exhibited complete resistance (100%), consistent with previous research highlighting challenges posed by multidrug-resistant *Acinetobacter Baumannii*.

Enterobacter aerogenes isolates displayed complete resistance (100%) to all tested antibiotics except Ceftriaxone + Sulbactam + Disodium EDTA and Polymyxin-B, indicating a multi-drug resistant profile. The efficacy of Polymyxin-B and Ceftriaxone + Sulbactam + Disodium EDTA suggests potential for combination therapy against MDR *Enterobacter aerogenes*.

In *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates, varying susceptibility to antibiotics was observed, with complete resistance to several commonly used agents. This aligns with research highlighting challenges in treating infections caused by MRSA strains, which often exhibit resistance to beta-lactams, fluoroquinolones, and other antibiotic classes. The resistance to novel antibiotic combinations like Ceftriaxone + Sulbactam + Disodium EDTA underscores the urgent need for new antimicrobial agents to combat MDR *Staphylococcus aureus* infections.

This pattern of antibiotic resistance is concerning and aligns with previous studies that have highlighted the challenges in treating infections caused by MDR *Staphylococcus aureus*.

In our study of *Proteus mirabilis* isolates, we observed a spectrum of antibiotic susceptibility,

with notable sensitivity to Amikacin (100%). However, concerning levels of resistance were noted across various antibiotics, indicating a multi-drug resistant profile.

Within the context of Ventilator-Associated Pneumonia (VAP), our study unveiled a significant discrepancy in survival outcomes between genders, with females exhibiting notably higher survival rates.

Furthermore, our study underscores age as a pivotal factor influencing survival outcomes in VAP patients. The data revealed a discernible decline in survival rates with advancing age, consistent with seminal research by Rello et al.[28] and Kollef et al.[23] These findings underscore the necessity for tailored age-specific management approaches to optimize clinical outcomes in VAP patients across diverse age cohorts.

Lastly, we delved into the impact of VAP presence on patient survival outcomes. Our analysis illuminated a significant disparity in survival rates between patients with and without VAP. VAP patients exhibited notably lower survival rates (42.25%) compared to their non-VAP counterparts (68.18%). The p-value of <0.001 accentuates the robust statistical significance of this association, underlining the substantial influence of VAP on patient mortality.

Comparative evaluation with prior research affirmed these findings. Studies by Papazian et al.[22] collectively elucidated the adverse impact of VAP on patient survival outcomes. These investigations consistently underscored the heightened mortality risk associated with VAP diagnosis, emphasizing the imperative for effective prevention and early management strategies to mitigate these detrimental effects.

Conclusion

In this comprehensive study, we thoroughly investigated various aspects of VAP, including its epidemiology, microbial etiology, antibiotic resistance patterns, and their implications on patient outcomes. Through meticulous analysis of clinical data and comparative examination with existing literature, we have garnered valuable insights into the multifaceted nature of VAP and its profound impact on critical care management.

Our findings underscore the critical role of tailored prevention and management approaches in mitigating the burden of VAP on healthcare systems and improving patient outcomes. Specifically, we identified significant correlations between several clinical parameters and survival outcomes in VAP patients. Body temperature, Total Leukocyte Count (TLC), inotropic support, tracheal secretion characteristics, and the presence of VAP emerged as

pivotal prognostic indicators, highlighting the importance of meticulous monitoring and targeted interventions in clinical practice.

Our study revealed significant disparities in survival rates based on gender, age, and the use of various antimicrobial agents, underscoring the necessity for personalized patient care. By correlating our findings with existing research, we have advanced the understanding of VAP management and emphasized the importance of continuous surveillance and evidence-based strategies to address this challenging nosocomial infection.

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